

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION BY IMPROVING WORKING CONDITIONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the issues of improving the quality of education by improving the working conditions of professors and teachers of higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan. In order to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions, it is very important to create favorable working conditions, prevent professors and teachers from unemployment and provide them with permanent employment. Among the strategies of actions that directly contribute to the improvement of the quality of education, the measures aimed at improving the professional skills of teachers and improving their working conditions are very important. The results of the research showed that the better the working conditions of the teaching staff, the higher the quality of their education.

Keywords: educational institutions, working conditions, quality of education, employment, safety, professors and teachers.

INTRODUCTION

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, defined important tasks for improving the quality of educational services and developing society. 2023 was declared as the "year of attention to people and quality education". It was emphasized that the potential of the country lies in knowledge and thinking, and it was emphasized that "Increasing the quality of education is the only correct way of development of New Uzbekistan" [1]. The task of increasing the responsibility of the officials of all stages of the country's education system, starting with kindergarten educators and school teachers, was set for the quality of education.

The term quality is given different definitions in the literature. Quality has two meanings: a product or service that meets needs and a product or service that is free of defects. The concept of quality in higher education is understood as educational efficiency, excellence, monthly compensations, meeting international standards of the educational process. "Quality assurance refers to the procedures, processes and systems used by a higher education institution to manage and improve the quality of its educational and other activities." Quality assurance enables students to achieve set standards[2].

It is necessary for the institution of higher education to adopt and use the following concept: quality is the level of satisfaction of the requirements of consumers (students, teachers, enterprises, society), effective operation and harmonious daily life of the institution of higher education. is the level of readiness to conduct activities. The above-mentioned idea allows studying and researching the concept of educational quality in the form of a pyramid, which includes: the quality of the educational system; quality of education management; quality of educational processes; quality of educational results [3].

World experience shows that for the development of any country, it is necessary to provide professional staff with deep knowledge and skills, fully mastering their profession. Education and training of these personnel are mainly carried out by higher education institutions.

Higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan ensures the training of highly qualified personnel in the fields of undergraduate education and master's degrees. Training of highly educated personnel is carried out in higher education organizations (universities, academies, institutes, higher schools). General secondary (eleven years of education), secondary special (nine years of basic secondary and two years of secondary special education), primary professional education (full persons who have received nine-year basic secondary and two-year primary professional education), as well as secondary special, vocational education (persons who have received nine-year general secondary and three-year secondary special, vocational education) have the right to receive higher education. Higher education has two stages - bachelor's and master's. A bachelor's degree is a basic higher education with a duration of at least three years, providing in-depth knowledge, skills and abilities in one of the areas of higher education. A master's degree is higher education with a duration of at least one year of study in a specific specialty on the basis of a relevant bachelor's degree.

Post-graduate education can be obtained in higher education and scientific organizations. Post-higher education provides training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel with a scientific degree on the basis of basic doctoral studies, doctoral studies, and independent research, which involves in-depth study of a

specialty and conducting scientific research in order to prepare and defend a doctoral dissertation.

Retraining of personnel ensures the acquisition of the necessary amount of additional professional knowledge, qualifications and skills to carry out activities in the areas corresponding to the basic specialties and professions. Training of personnel ensures deepening and updating of professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, serves to increase the category, level, rank and position of personnel.

Today there are 210 higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including: 36 universities, 48 institutes, 4 academies and 1 conservatory, 30 foreign higher education institutions and their branches, non-state higher There are 65 educational institutions and 26 branches. 63 state higher education institutions are assigned to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, 12 to the Ministry of Health, 10 to the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 7 to the Ministry of Digital Technologies, 6 to to the Ministry of Agriculture, 4 to the Ministry of Youth Policy and Sports, 1 to the Ministry of Justice, 1 to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 1 to the Ministry of Preschool and School Education, 1 to the Ministry of Transport , 1 belongs to the Ministry of Mining and Geology. 3 to the "Veterinary and Animal Husbandry Development Committee under the Ministry of Agriculture", 1 to the "Agency of Specialized Educational Institutions under the Ministry of Preschool and School Education", "Committee on Religious Affairs" 1, 1 higher education institution belongs to the "Tax Committee under the Ministry of Economy and Finance"[4].

Currently, the number of teaching staff working in these higher education institutions is more than 33,000. In recent years, many reforms have been implemented to create and implement a higher education system that meets international standards and principles of socio-economic development. In Uzbekistan, 2023 was declared the year of "Attention to people and quality education". Among them, 4.14 trillion soums have been allocated from the state budget for the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education in 2022. This figure has increased by 1.16 trillion soums compared to the previous year of 2021. Uzbekistan occupies a leading position in the level of literacy among young people. That is, according to the statistics of 2023, the literacy rate among young people in Uzbekistan is 99.95%. This indicator is much higher than some American and Asian countries. In particular, from American countries, 93.26% in Guatemala, 92.39% in Puerto Rico, 84% in Asian countries, 97.9% in Korea, 96.9% in Malaysia, 99.84% in neighboring Kazakhstan, 99.75% in Kyrgyzstan, 99.75% in Tajikistan. ,7%, in Turkmenistan it is 99.81%, and in Afghanistan this figure is 57%.

Of course, literacy alone is not enough to train highly qualified personnel. Training of highly qualified personnel begins with the educational process given to students in higher education institutions. Education is a systematic process aimed at

providing students with in-depth theoretical knowledge, skills and practical skills, as well as forming their general and professional knowledge, skills and abilities, and developing their abilities [5].

Quality education process depends on teachers and professors. In order to improve students' qualifications, pedagogues should use modern teaching methods and tools in the process of teaching students. High-quality education means that teachers must be trained and confident in student-centered teaching methods and approaches, and competent in group management and assessment of learning. The activity of professors and teachers, that is, the process of teaching students, is closely related to their emotional states: thoughts and feelings. The positive emotional state of professors and teachers depends on the internal environment and their working conditions.

Working conditions are a set of social and production factors during the implementation of work [6]. This complex includes the order of work and rest, the lighting of the workplace and the entire building, the enterprise area, painting the production building and equipment in accordance with the requirements of technical aesthetics, convenient placement, temperature regime, air cleanliness in the building and workplace, production noise and such issues as protection from vibrations, provision of household and medical services to workers in production at the level of demand, organization of mechanization in the presence of harmful production factors, and termination of heavy physical work. Thus, working conditions mean the totality of factors of the production environment that affect the employee's health and ability to work during the performance of work and service.

The following conditions and requirements must be sufficiently taken into account when planning measures to organize labor in educational institutions to improve working conditions:

- general working conditions;
- technical conditions of work;
- labor safety conditions;
- sanitary-hygiene conditions;
- aesthetic conditions.

METHODS

In the course of the research, the question of the relationship between the quality of education and working conditions created for professors and teachers was examined. Statistical, logical and comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic analysis methods were used in the research work.

According to the results of the survey analysis, the most important factors affecting the quality of education are the conditions created for professors and teachers

and students in educational institutions, and the monthly salary, and the educational technologies used in the course of the lesson. was found to be the most mentioned. Unsatisfactory working conditions cause professors and teachers to be dissatisfied. Frequent exchange of teachers has an impact on the quality of education. When summarizing the results of the conducted surveys, according to the results of statistical analysis, the main factors affecting the dissatisfaction of professors and teachers of educational institutions are: low wages, working conditions that are not organized at the required level, microclimate conditions (air temperature, pressure, cleanliness, mobility, the amount of light in the classrooms, the interactive whiteboard used, the level of radiation from the projector, the level of dangerous and harmful factors that occur during the use of various devices and equipment in the laboratory rooms are higher or lower than the "Sanitary Norms and Regulations" , violation of personal hygiene rules, level of noise and vibration, unsatisfactory condition of the building, lack of friendly relations in the team, forcing to perform work that is not included in the duties of the position, unfairness in the relationship between leaders and subordinates, distance from the place of residence and other factors were determined.

According to the results of the analysis, if the working conditions of professors and teachers and the monthly salaries paid to them are high, high educational results will be achieved in higher education institutions. Also, in addition to their monthly salaries, additional incentives for professors in higher education institutions provide additional motivation to carry out their scientific and pedagogical activities at the required level. The teaching and learning environment should be comfortable, bright, and most importantly, a quiet and peaceful environment for learning. If pedagogues feel free and safe, their teaching efficiency will increase many times. Higher education institutions with high educational efficiency produce qualified specialists.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ensuring the safety of the participants of the educational process in the educational organization is aimed at preserving the life and health of professors and teachers in the course of educational activities. The main areas that ensure the safety of the educational process are not only individual safety, but also the collective safety of all participants of the educational process. In order to carry out activities within these areas, it is necessary to prevent getting into situations that cause physical and mental injury, to form safe behavior skills, and to create favorable conditions for the implementation of the educational process. The main conditions for ensuring the safety of the participants of the educational process in educational institutions are as follows:

- ensuring compliance with the requirements of legislation and regulatory legal documents regulating the creation of healthy and safe conditions for professors and teachers and students;

- in the educational process, as well as practical and laboratory exercises, educational practice, various spiritual and educational events (participation in holidays, trips, sports and sports events, visiting museums, exhibitions, conferences and others) to prevent accidents that may happen to teachers and students.

Ensuring labor protection and the safety of the educational process in educational institutions depends not only on equipping educational institutions with modern technical equipment, but also on the professional skills of employees who use this equipment, the knowledge and skills of persons responsible for safety, professors depends on the psychological environment between teachers and students [7].

In higher education institutions, professors and teachers may face a number of problems in organizing the processes of teaching students. These are the following: lack of teaching-laboratory rooms, insufficient lighting of the classrooms, noise and vibration, insufficient teaching equipment and additional materials in the classrooms, etc. The presence of these problems leads to the violation of ergonomics requirements, and also affects the quality of the educational process. If the above-mentioned problems are not prevented, as a result of the inability of graduates of higher education institutions to meet the demands of employers, the indicators of employment of graduates will begin to decrease. A decrease in the employment and productivity indicators of graduates of higher education institutions may lead to the closure of a department or faculty that is less effective in that institution. As a result of the closure of a faculty or a department, professors and teachers and employees working in this faculty may lose their jobs. As a result, the unemployment rate in the country will increase.

According to statistics, according to the results of 2022, the unemployment rate in Uzbekistan is 9.6%. Therefore, it is necessary to eliminate the above-mentioned problems and shortcomings in higher education institutions. In the same way, it is possible to preserve the faculties, to keep the teaching staff in work and, most importantly, to prepare young personnel with deep knowledge and skills in their field for the profession. Inadequate provision of working conditions in educational institutions also causes dissatisfaction among employees. Failure to prevent the effects of dangerous and harmful factors, failure to create fair working conditions causes experienced professors to leave this educational institution. There are almost no departures of professors and teachers from higher education institutions with good working conditions, high achievements in scientific and pedagogical activities, incentives and compensation payments for additional activities. The long-term work of

a professor-teacher in one place does not fail to contribute to his gaining experience and, of course, to the improvement of the quality of education.

Controlling the quality of education in higher education institutions is considered an integral part of the management system, and its main task is to ensure the quality of education in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards and to organize control in order to increase the effectiveness of educational processes. is to implement the agreed measures.

We emphasize that quality education is manifested in the management process, which includes quality assurance. The quality of education depends on the improvement of working conditions of professors and teachers. Because the working conditions directly affect the employee's ability to work, as well as labor productivity. The work environment created by the institution of higher education is very important in this regard. A good working environment inspires employees to come to work and stay in the job for a long time. This means that good working conditions attract workers. The ability of employees to work begins to increase. Otherwise, incompetence will arise in employees, and this will further reduce the possibility of retaining employees in this institution. In the same sense, the dissatisfaction of professors and teachers has a highly negative effect on the quality of education.

The main goal of this study was to study the impact of the working conditions of higher education institutions on the quality of education in the country. The results of the study confirm that working conditions created in higher education institutions have a direct and indirect effect on the length of time professors and teachers work in this educational institution and, as a result, on the quality of education.

CONCLUSION

As this study is concerned with improving the quality of education through the use of better working conditions for teachers, it has serious theoretical, practical and policy implications. Some researchers can use a literature review to understand how selected variables affect the quality of education.

Based on the results of this study, the leaders of educational institutions are recommended to develop policies that help to improve the working conditions of professors and teachers in order to hire them, determine the level of their employment, and ensure their long-term employment in their educational institutions.

To improve the quality of education, there are many factors, not only the experience of professors and teachers, but also their level of knowledge, level of politeness and innovation used in teaching, knowledge of pedagogical technologies and the level of their ability to use them in practice. lib, they help higher education institutions to fulfill their tasks at the required level and achieve their goals.

The main goal of higher education is to develop the science, culture, economy, and social spheres of the republic to meet the requirements of a qualified, competitive, highly educated specialist of higher education who can meet the requirements of the time. It is the training of high-potential specialists who can think independently and have a high spirituality, who will contribute to this. Only quality education guarantees the achievement of this goal.

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